

Based on the paper "**Electron Geometry**".

A crude attempted visualization of a possible electron toroidal quantum orbit is plotted.
It is unlikely to be numerically viable.

Done with Maple software:

restart : with(plots) :

local beta, gamma :

Digits := 24 : interface(displayprecision = 6) :

βe_1 : and γe_1 : are temperature-reduced values in meters from the paper "**Electron Geometry**":

$\beta e_1 := 2.644842743E-11 :$

$\gamma e_1 := 2.644561075E-11 :$

$\alpha := .0072973526 :$

γ is the major radius and β is the minor radius of a toroidal orbit, normalized here to $\beta=1$ for plotting.

$\beta := 1.0 : \gamma := \frac{\gamma e_1}{\beta e_1} = 0.999894$ gamma scaled for beta equal to 1

$j := 2.0 :$ Index j sets 2 beta orbits for 1 electron orbit cycle.

$i := 2.0 \cdot \frac{\gamma e_1}{\gamma e_1 + \beta e_1} = 0.999947$ Index i scales gamma path from electron radii, 2 per orbit cycle

Torus formula R:

$R := (a, b) \rightarrow \langle (\gamma + \beta \cdot \cos(b)) \cos(a), (\gamma + \beta \cdot \cos(b)) \sin(a), \beta \cdot \sin(b) \rangle :$

$k := 1.0 :$ Plot index k sets number of cycles of electron orbit to plot.

Plot definition:

$plot3d(R(a, b), a = 0 .. 2 \pi, b = 0 .. 2.0 \pi, scaling = constrained, axes = none, colorscheme = ["gray", "gray"], style = wireframe, transparency = .40) : F := % :$

$spacecurve(R(i \cdot a, j \cdot a), a = 0 .. k \cdot 2 \cdot \pi, colorscheme = ["black", "gray"], thickness = 0, numpoints = 5000, transparency = .00) : G := % :$

"Top" view: $display((F, G), orientation = [0, 0, 0]);$

"Side" view: $display((F, G), orientation = [0, 90, 0])$

"Side" view rotated 90 degrees: $display((F, G), orientation = [90, 90, 0])$

Tilted "Side" view rotated 90 degrees: $display((F, G), orientation = [90, 60, 0])$

$k := \frac{0.25}{\alpha^2} = 4694.716222$ Plot index k sets number of cycles for about half of full quantum orbit.

"Top" view:

```
plot3d(R(a, b), a = 0 .. 2 * pi, b = 0 .. 2 * pi, orientation = [0, 0, 0], scaling = constrained, axes = none,
  colorscheme = ["gray", "gray"], style = wireframe, transparency = .40) : F := %:
spacecurve(R( i * a, j * a), a = 0 .. k * 2 * pi, colorscheme = ["black", "gray"], thickness = 0, numpoints
  = 50000, transparency = .00) : G := %: display(F, G);
```

